

Digital Security Innovations in 2025 by COREnext

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Welcome to the Latest Achievements of the COREnext Project!

In this edition, we bring you the latest updates from the 3rd COREnext Plenary Meeting in Frankfurt/Oder, where partners gathered to review progress and plan the final steps of the project. We also highlight recent scientific publications, key project reports, and introduce you to the people behind COREnext, driving innovation in next-generation computing and networking.

Dive into the latest insights and stay connected with COREnext!

COREnext News

[COREnext 3rd Plenary Meeting: Progress, Demonstrations, and Future Plans](#)

Discover key project updates on digital security, real-world testing, and platform integration, along with innovative tech demos from Ericsson AB, Nokia, Barkhausen Institut, and imec. Get insights into our roadmap for the final year and see how COREnext is shaping tomorrow's technology landscape!

[Read more](#)

Watch the short reportage from the Plenary Meeting now!

From Digital & Trustworthy Analogue Components ensuring security and reliability, to Lab Validators testing real-world applications, and progress on the Computation-Communication Platform - the foundation of future tech is being built right here.

[Watch the video](#)

D1.4 Second Year Management Report

This COREnext report connects the deliverables submitted in year two to the project objectives. D1.4 reports on work performed within the work packages, summarizes achievements and risks, and finally concludes by analysing feedback we received from the project's mid-term review.

[Read more](#)

Don't miss out!

Dive into the Future of Digitalisation with Our Latest White Paper!

Uncover how trust and security are shaping the evolution of Europe's dominance in high-end consumer goods. Discover how the fusion of connectivity and sensing technologies is revolutionising product value and seamlessly weaving these innovations into consumers' digital lives.

[Download our White Paper](#)

COREnext In Science Hub

Welcome to the [Scientific Publications section of COREnext](#), a dynamic hub for the scientific and literature stemming from our European project.

READ MORE

#COREnextInScience

[Circularly Polarized Sub-THz Antenna Design for Distributed Deployment](#)

In this paper, the writers propose an antenna-in-package concept for the single-layer substrate on low-cost embedded wafer level ball grid array.

[Read more](#)

READ MORE

#COREnextInScience

[Towards Modular Trusted Execution Environments](#)

In this conference workshop the authors propose a modular TEE design. They apply this modular design to the M3 hardware/software co-design platform and demonstrate how TEE support can be made a first-class feature at the system-architecture level.

[Read more](#)

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COREnext In The Spotlight

Women In Science Day in COREnext

“Science and everyday life cannot and should not be separated.” – Rosalind Franklin.

Days like #WomenInScience Day on 11th February remind us of the importance of visibility and inclusion in #STEM, ensuring the next generation of female innovators has the support they need to thrive.

Meet the incredible women of COREnext! From technical experts to science communicators, our team members bring different perspectives and skills to drive innovation forward. Follow their profiles and get inspired by their journeys in STEM!

[Frida Strömbeck](#) | [Vanessa Daccache](#)
| [Manuela Neyer](#) | [Zulaicha Parastuty](#)
| [María Culell Elustondo](#) | [Agnieszka Mikołajczyk](#)

[Discover more](#)

Zulaicha Parastuty
Innovation, Funding Cooperation

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CORENEXT
IN THE SPOTLIGHT

[#COREnextInTheSpotlight: Meet Zulaicha Parastuty from Infineon!](#)

Today, under the umbrella of #COREnextInTheSpotlight campaign we are celebrating achievements of Zulaicha Parastuty - representative of Infineon Technologies 🙌

At Infineon Technologies, Austria, Dr. Zulaicha Parastuty manages EU and Austrian funding projects, as well as pre-development initiatives, driving innovation and cooperation in the realm of Radio Frequency and Sensors.

[Find out more](#)

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CORENEXT is an EU-funded initiative that will bring together expert stakeholders in future mobile networks and integrate their perspectives in key focus areas like digital, analogue, and integrated solutions for computing, communication, and sensing.

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